

Chemical Studies of Some Heterocyclic Compounds with Pharmacological Possibilities: 2-Nitrophenylbenzofuran

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Synthesis of several 2-*p*-nitrophenylbenzofurans by reacting *o*-hydroxyketones with 4-nitrobenzyl bromide has been effected.

In recent communications¹ preparation of a number of substituted aroylbenzofurans as possible estrogens has been described. The present paper reports the synthesis of some 2-*p*-nitrophenylbenzofurans, required for some pharmacological studies.

Stoermer² reported that cyclisation of *o*-benzyloxybenzaldehyde (II: R=R'=R''=H) to 2-phenylbenzofuran (III: R=R'=R''=H) could not be accomplished unless sodium was used as a condensing agent in an atmosphere of hydrogen. The yield even then was poor. Recently Mathur and Mehra³ reported a synthesis of 2-*p*-nitrophenylbenzofuran (III: R=R'=H, R''=NO₂) as main product by condensing 4-nitrobenzyl bromide with salicylaldehyde, although 4-chlorobenzyl bromide failed to provide a cyclic product under identical conditions and yielded only 2-*p*-chlorobenzoyloxybenzaldehyde (II: R=R'=H, R''=Cl). We have found that the reaction of *o*-hydroxyacetophenones and *o*-hydroxypropionophenones with 4-nitrobenzyl bromide in presence of freshly ignited potassium carbonate in methanol, kept for 9 hours on a steam bath, gave 2-*p*-nitrophenylbenzofurans in good yields. When a reaction mixture of 2-hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenone (I: R=Cl, R'=Me) and 4-nitrobenzyl bromide, kept under identical conditions, is worked up, after 45 minutes, 2-*p*-nitrobenzyloxy-5-chloroacetophenone (II: R=Cl, R'=Me, R''=NO₂) is isolated in almost quantitative yield. This compound readily gives 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone and oxime. 2-*p*-Nitrobenzyloxy-5-chloroacetophenone undergoes cyclisation to 2-*p*-nitrophenyl-3-methyl-5-chlorobenzofuran (III: R=Cl, R'=Me, R''=NO₂), when treated with potassium carbonate in methanol, ethanolic potassium hydroxide, or sodium ethoxide, the last two affording smooth cyclisation.

1. Singh and Kapil, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, 24, 2064; this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 695.

2. *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 3979.

3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 1954.

TABLE I

<i>o</i> -Hydroxyketone.	Benzofuran formed.	Colour.	Yield.	*M.P.	Cryst. form.	Colour with conc. sulphuric acid.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
2-Hydroxy-A	2- <i>p</i> -N-3-methyl-	Canary yellow needles	75%	140°	Acetic acid	Blue-black	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₃ N	C: 70.9% H: 4.4 N: 5.4	71.2% 4.3 5.5
2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-A	2- <i>p</i> -N-3,6-dimethyl-	Yellow needles	70	125°	"	Brown (turning deep)	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ N	C: 71.7 H: 5.0 N: 5.1	71.9 4.9 5.2
2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-A	2- <i>p</i> -N-3,5-dimethyl-	Orange-yellow needles	75	137°	"	Deep violet	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ N	C: 71.8 H: 5.0 N: 5.2	71.9 4.9 5.2
2-Hydroxy-5-bromo-A	2- <i>p</i> -N-3-methyl-5-bromo-	Yellow flakes	75	100°	"	Pink (turning dark orange)	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₃ NBr	Br: 23.8	24.1
2-Hydroxy-5-chloro-A	2- <i>p</i> -N-3-methyl-5-chloro-	Light orange-yellow flakes	70	202°	AcOH-EtOH	Deep violet	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₃ NCl	Cl: 12.0	12.3
2-Hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methyl-A	2- <i>p</i> -N-3,5-dimethyl-7-bromo-	Yellow	65	164°	Acetic acid	Violet	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ NBr	Br: 22.8	23.1
2-Hydroxy-3-bromo-5-chloro-A	2- <i>p</i> -N-3-methyl-5-chloro-7-bromo-	Dirty yellow	60	230°	AcOH + benzene	Pink	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₃ NClBr	Br + Cl: 31.2	31.5
2-Hydroxy-5-bromo-P	2- <i>p</i> -N-3-ethyl-5-bromo-	Light yellow needles	70	155°	Acetic acid	"	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ NBr	Br: 23.0	23.1
2-Hydroxy-5-chloro-P	2- <i>p</i> -N-3-ethyl-5-chloro-	Light yellow needles	70	148°	"	Light pink (turning orange)	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ NCl	Cl: 11.6	11.8

*All melting points are uncorrected.
A, P, and N denote respectively acetophenone, propiophenone, and nitrophenyl.

The 2-*p*-nitrophenylbenzofurans obtained are coloured, crystalline solids, insoluble in water, and not very much soluble in ethanol. They exhibit halochromy with concentrated sulphuric acid and do not react with carbonyl reagents.

EXPERIMENTAL

o-Hydroxyketones were prepared by the Fries migration of the respective phenyl esters⁴.

4-Nitrobenzyl bromide was synthesised by direct bromination of *p*-nitrotoluene at 145-50° and the product was recrystallised with petroleum ether⁵ (b.p. 80-100°).

2-*p*-Nitrophenylbenzofuran.—A mixture of *o*-hydroxyketone (0.05*M*), 4-nitrobenzyl bromide (0.05*M*), and freshly ignited potassium carbonate (0.06*M*) in methanol (80.0 ml) was refluxed on a steam bath for 9 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled, and the precipitate filtered, washed with methanol, and then with water. The product was collected and recrystallised from a suitable solvent using activated charcoal whenever necessary. The compounds prepared are recorded in Table I.

When wetted with concentrated sulphuric acid, the 2-*p*-nitrophenylbenzofurans exhibit halochromism.

2-*p*-Nitrobenzyl-5-chloroacetophenone.—A mixture of 2-hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenone (8.5 g.), 4-nitrobenzyl bromide (10.8 g.), and freshly ignited potassium carbonate (8.0 g.) in methanol (80.0 ml) was refluxed on a steam bath for 45 minutes and cooled; the precipitated solid was filtered and washed with dilute methanol and then with water. Recrystallisation of the product from acetic acid gave colorless needles (13.5 g.), m.p. 154°. (Found: Cl, 11.5. C₁₅H₁₂O₄NCl requires Cl, 11.6%).

2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone (from ethyl acetate), m.p. 252°. (Found: N, 14.5. C₂₁H₁₆O₇N₃Cl requires N, 14.4%).

Oxime (from ethanol), m.p. 157°. (Found: Cl, 10.9. C₁₅H₁₃O₄N₂Cl requires Cl, 11.1%).

Cyclisation of 2-*p*-nitrobenzyl-5-chloroacetophenone to 2-*p*-nitrophenyl-3-*m*-ethyl-5-chlorobenzofuran was accomplished by the following methods.

(i) A mixture of 2-*p*-nitrobenzyl-5-chloroacetophenone (1.0 g.) and freshly ignited potassium carbonate (1.0 g.) in methanol (8.0 ml) was refluxed on a steam bath for 8 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and the precipitated solid filtered, washed with methanol and then with water. The product was recrystallised from acetic acid (charcoal), giving shining, light orange flakes (0.7 g.), m.p. 202°.

(ii) To a solution of potassium hydroxide (0.5 g.) in ethanol (8.0 ml) was added 2-*p*-nitrobenzyl-5-chloroacetophenone (1.0 g.) and the mixture was refluxed on a steam bath for 30 minutes (The colorless reaction mixture gradually changed to dark orange). It was cooled and the precipitated solid was filtered and recrystallised from acetic acid (0.7 g.), m.p. 202°.

4. *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 4271.

5. Vogel, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd ed., 1956, Longmans Green and Company, p. 961.

(iii) To a solution of sodium ethoxide from sodium (0.25 g.) and ethanol (18.0 ml) 2-*p*-nitrobenzyloxy-5-chloroacetophenone (1.0 g.) was added and the reaction mixture kept on a steam bath. The ketone went into solution, the colour of the reaction mixture changed to dark orange, and shining crystals of benzofuran started separating. After 20 minutes' heating it was worked up as in the previous case, m.p. 202°, yield 0.8 g.

The benzofuran obtained in all the three cases gave deep violet halochromy with concentrated sulphuric acid and their mixed melting point determinations with a sample obtained by other methods showed no depression.

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